

101132933 – AD-RIDDLE

Real-World Implementation, Deployment and Validation of Early Detection Tools and Lifestyle Enhancement

WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation

D3.1 Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents	2
Document History	3
Definitions	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Methods	6
2.1 Fluid based biomarkers included in WP3.....	7
2.2 Clinical sites planned to be included in WP3	8
3. Results	8
3.1 Blood collection protocol.....	9
3.2 Prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms 10	
3.3 Assessing impact of BBMs on the diagnostic work-up, patient flow and management in real- world settings	11
3.4 Improving the use of BBMs to identify individuals with preclinical AD.....	13
4. Discussion	13
5. Conclusion	14

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	15 October 2024	First Draft
V1.1	30 October 2024	First draft shared with WP3 partners
V1.2	13 December	Draft for clinical sites review
V1.3	16 December	Draft for Ad-Riddle PMO
V1.4	31 December	Final Version

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the AD-RIDDLE Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

RS: Region Stockholm, Karolinska Universitetssjukhuset - Sweden (**The Coordinator**)

KI: Karolinska Institutet, Department of Neurobiology, Care Sciences and Society - Sweden

FBHI: Stiftelsen Fingers Brain Health Institute - Sweden

UGOT: Goteborgs Universitet - Sweden

ULUND: Lunds Universitet - Sweden

UEF: Itä-Suomen Yliopisto, University of Eastern Finland - Finland

VUMC: Stichting VUmc - The Netherlands

UM: Universiteit Maastricht - The Netherlands

BBRC: Fundació Barcelonabeta Brain Research Center - Spain

SYNAPSE: Synapse Research Management Partners S.L - Spain

AE: Alzheimer Europe - Luxembourg

ADI: Alzheimer's Disease International – United States

UNIPG: Università Degli Studi di Perugia - Italy

GV: Gates Ventures LLC – United States (**The Co-Coordinator**)

DAC: Davos Alzheimer's Collaborative - Switzerland

COMBINOSTICS: Combinostics Oy - Finland

Fujirebio: Fujirebio Europe NV - Belgium

SARD: Sanofi-Aventis Recherche & Development - France

C2N: C2N Diagnostics LLC – United States

neotiv GmbH: Neotiv GmbH - Germany

CCL: Cambridge Cognition Limited – United Kingdom

ULEIC: University of Leicester – United Kingdom

ICL: Imperial College of Science, Technology and medicine - United Kingdom

NICE: National Institute for Health and Care Excellence- United Kingdom

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IHI for the undertaking of the AD-RIDDLE project (101132933).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The AD-RIDDLE Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst AD-RIDDLE participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Alzheimer’s disease (AD) and related neurodegenerative disorders are among the most significant global health challenges, with 55 million people currently living with dementia. This number is expected to grow to 130 million by 2050 due to aging populations and a lack of effective therapies. When including prodromal and preclinical stages of AD, over 400 million people worldwide are estimated to be affected, representing approximately 22% of individuals aged 50 or older. The economic burden is substantial, with global dementia costs exceeding \$1.3 trillion annually and European costs comparable to those of all cancers and cardiovascular diseases combined. Current diagnostic methods in primary care and specialist memory clinics show high misdiagnosis rates, highlighting the urgent need for improved tools. To address these challenges, the AD-RIDDLE Consortium WP3 has focused on validating novel blood-based biomarkers (BBMs) for AD diagnosis in diverse, real-world clinical settings. These biomarkers include A β 42/40 ratio, phosphorylated tau (p-tau), neurofilament light chain (NFL), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP). Prospective validation of BBMs, integrated with brief cognitive assessments, can revolutionize early diagnosis and care by accurately predicting short-term clinical decline in patients with mild memory complaints. The project has been developing a harmonized Core Protocol for testing BBMs across multiple European sites, co-designed with industry partners. Site-specific sub-study protocols will detail recruitment, clinical settings, and biomarker sets to be tested. Rigorous laboratory protocols and quality control measures will be implemented, and ethical approvals will be secured. Additionally, collaborations with industry partners have facilitated protocol development for evaluating BBMs' diagnostic and prognostic utility in both memory and primary care clinics. Looking ahead, the consortium will continue with conducting prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms and improving the use of BBMs to additionally identify individuals with preclinical AD. By advancing these efforts, the project aims to enhance diagnostic accuracy, reduce misdiagnosis, and pave the way for effective integration of BBMs into clinical practice worldwide.

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
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1. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's and related neurodegenerative diseases (AD) are one of the biggest global health challenges of our time (World Health Organization 2012, 2017; Alzheimer's Disease International. 2019). Today, there are 55 million people with dementia. With global population ageing (Eurostat 2023) and current lack of widely available effective therapies, this number is estimated to grow to 130 million by 2050 (World Health Organization 2021). With persons with prodromal and preclinical AD, estimated at 69 and 315 million respectively (Gustavsson et al, 2023), this constitutes >400 million people across the entire AD continuum, or ≈22% of all people aged 50+. In Europe alone, it is estimated that 14.1 million people currently live with dementia with a cost burden of 409 Bn EUR. The magnitude of this is similar to the combined cost of all cancers (EUR 199Bn) (Hofmarcher et al, 2020) and cardiovascular diseases (EUR 210 Bn) (Wilkins et al, 2017). With global costs of dementia already exceeding \$1.3 trillion (Gauthier et al, 2022), this represents an increasing threat to global health and societal sustainability, unless effective preventive and therapeutic solutions are identified and implemented.

Among the highest priorities in AD biomarker research is evaluation of high-performing BBMs in diverse (real-world) populations in both memory and primary care clinics, inclusive of diversity across demographics, comorbidities, ethnicity, care setting, and more. To truly determine clinical robustness, these biomarkers should be studied prospectively (Hansson et al, 2022). According to recent international recommendations, novel blood assays should be used in extended prospective studies over several years where (1) pre-defined cut-offs are used, (2) samples are analysed continuously (e.g., on a bi-weekly basis rather than in single batches), and (3) an appropriate reference standard is used (including CSF or PET AD biomarkers) (Hansson et al, 2022). To date, no studies have been published in which high-performing AD BBMs were prospectively and rigorously validated in patients with memory impairment in memory clinics, and certainly not in primary care. Therefore, we will study the clinical robustness and accuracy of plasma AD biomarkers prospectively in real-world settings. Given the excellent infrastructure of the primary care system in many of our selected European countries and research biomarker protocols already approved and fully integrated in clinical practice, we have a unique opportunity to test these novel AD BBMs in broad, diverse, and unselected populations that are generalizable to other real-world settings.

2. METHODS

AD-RIDDLE Consortium members have recently achieved major breakthroughs in accurate blood-based AD biomarkers, which have the potential to truly revolutionize AD diagnostics, e.g., A β 42/40 ratio, phosphorylated (p)-tau217, p-Tau231, p-Tau181, neurofilament light chain (NFL, neurodegeneration marker), and glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP, early marker of A β -related reactive astrogliosis) (Hansson O, 2021; Hansson et al, 2022). However, such novel biomarkers must now be thoroughly and prospectively validated in clinical practice before they can be implemented in specialist or primary care clinics, globally. This validation is urgently needed, as diagnostic accuracy of a work-up (without support of AD biomarkers) is limited with ~25-30% misdiagnosis of AD patients in specialist memory clinics and >50% in primary care (Hansson et al, 2022). Further, we should determine in which patients or real-world clinical settings these novel AD BBMs improve diagnosis, treatment, and care. We also need accurate prognostic tools to identify individuals with early AD who are most likely to experience short-term clinical decline because they need interventions. AD-RIDDLE Consortium members have shown that AD BBMs, together with brief cognitive tests, have very high accuracy to predict future development of dementia in specialist memory clinic patients with mild memory complaints (Palmqvist et al, 2021).

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
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2.1 Fluid based biomarkers included in WP3

Based on the research findings outlined above, a carefully selected set of blood-based biomarkers (BBMs) has been chosen for inclusion in this WP. The final selection was determined following a series of organized meetings and discussions. The initial two meetings, held prior to summer 2024 (12 March 2024 and 7 May 2024) involved representatives from all participating clinical sites. During these meetings, each clinical site presented its capabilities and resources for contributing to WP3. These discussions provided a comprehensive understanding of the collective expertise and infrastructure available across the consortium. Additionally, the real-world testing and validation of the selected BBMs were addressed in additional meetings held on 30 July 2024, 15 October 2024, 30 October 2024 and a series of individual meetings. Each clinical site engaged in detailed discussions with relevant industry partners, focusing on the practical implementation and evaluation of key biomarkers in real-world settings. These collaborative efforts concluded on the meeting on 13 December 2024 ensured that the selected biomarkers are not only scientifically robust but also practical and scalable for clinical applications.

Table 1. Summary table of biomarkers to be investigated in WP3 and WP4 in AD RIDDLE

	Blood-based biomarkers and other fluid biomarkers
Fujirebio	Lumipulse® G β -Amyloid 1-42, β -Amyloid 1-40, and pTau 181 Plasma (Research Use Only) Lumipulse assays for pTau217 and Neurofilament Light (NfL) Plasma (Under development, available 2024) Lumipulse® G β -Amyloid 1-42, β -Amyloid 1-40, pTau 181, Total Tau CSF (CE-marked)
SARD	Single molecule tau proteome analysis (Under development) Quanterix based pTau217 assay (Under development) Proteomic approach to identify multiple phospho-epitopes simultaneously PTau217 assay
C2N	PrecisionAD2® (β -Amyloid 42/40 & p-tau217 ratio) Plasma
UGOT	Plasma pTau231, Glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP), Simoa-based (Research Use Only)
	Plasma pTau217, Simoa-based (Clinical use in Sweden, since 06.2023)
	Plasma NfL, Simoa-based (Clinical use: Sweden, since 05.2021; Finland, 10.2022)
	Plasma β -synuclein, mass-spectrometry & Simoa-based (Research Use Only)
	Plasma Synaptosomal-Associated Protein (SNAP25), in collaboration with ADx (Research Use Only)
Other exploratory fluid biomarkers to be considered during the project **	
AD polygenic risk scores – Literature (e.g. De Rojas et al, 2021; Bellenguez et al, 2022) & collaborations with European Alzheimer’s Disease Biobank (EADB) Consortium	
Omics, e.g., metabolomics, proteomics; synaptic markers (e.g., neurogranin and SNAP25), inflammation, oxidative stress, related - Existing methods and/or potential new developments by industry or academic partners during the project	

**Exploratory fluid biomarkers will also be tested in the project (WP4), based on ongoing work by Consortium partners. Given AD heterogeneity, we and others have performed studies to define AD continuum subtypes (Tijms et al, 2020; Sandebring-Matton et al, 2021; Poulakis et al, 2022) using CSF and neuroimaging markers. New CSF-based biological strata were also identified in a memory clinic cohort, using established AD biomarkers (A β 42, p-Tau, t-Tau), synaptic markers (e.g., neurogranin and SNAP25), inflammatory markers, antioxidants, and proteins related to the vascular system and insulin resistance (Daniilidou et al., unpublished). Our data show that the studied biological pathways are divergent early in pathogenesis. The key drivers of each biological cluster may be relevant to evaluate as future intervention targets.

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó		Security: 8/14

2.2 Clinical sites planned to be included in WP3

Table 2. Brief description of the clinical sites involved in WP3 AD RIDDLE

Clinical sites	Brief description
Karolinska University Hospital, part of Region Stockholm (Sweden)	One of the largest EU university hospitals, ranked highest in Europe and sixth worldwide. Medical Unit Aging has strong expertise on dementia diseases with large patient flows, Unit for Clinical Trials, and extensive experience with biomarker and other AD studies. Recently, it opened a Brain Health Clinic to facilitate early implementation of dementia prevention.
The University of Gothenburg (UGOT) and Sahlgrenska University Hospital (Sweden)	The Clinical Neurochemistry laboratory at UGOT is world-leading on the development and validation of fluid biomarkers for AD and other dementia diseases; it is an accredited biomarker laboratory providing services to clinics/hospitals.
Lund University (LU) and Skåne University Hospital (Sweden)	Clinical Memory Research Unit and Memory Clinic conducting world-leading research on fluid biomarkers for AD/dementias.
VUmc (the Netherlands)	Leading Dutch dementia centre and largest memory clinic. The VUmc Neurochemistry lab has a global leading role in development of fluid biomarkers for AD/dementias and is the biomarker core of the Alzheimer Center in patient care, research and trials.
University of Eastern Finland (UEF) and Kuopio University Hospital (Finland)	The UEF Department of Neurology conducts epidemiological, clinical, and basic research on AD/dementia diseases. The department has an accredited biomarker laboratory for neurodegenerative diseases and an experienced clinical trials unit, connected to the highly specialized memory clinic at Kuopio University Hospital.
Imperial College London (IMPERIAL) and Imperial College NHS Healthcare Trust (UK)	The AGE Unit has an established collaboration with primary care practices in the wider London area via the CHARIOT register for dementia research, and an experienced clinical trials unit for AD/dementias conducting both large-scale observational studies and pharmaceutical randomised clinical trials.
Barcelonabeta Brain Research Center (BBRC, Spain)	BBRC focuses on research on AD prevention and healthy aging based on studies within clinical, cognitive, genetic, and fluid and imaging biomarker fields. BBRC has its own Fluid Biomarker Facility and Neuroimaging Platform.
University of Perugia (UNIPG) Section of Gerontology and Geriatrics (Italy)	Includes a memory clinic, accredited fluid biomarkers laboratory for AD/dementias, and an experienced clinical trials unit conducting epidemiological, clinical, and basic AD/dementia research.

3. RESULTS

We have been developing a Core Protocol for harmonized real-world testing of BBMs across multiple different clinical sites (and their respective healthcare systems) in different countries. This has been harmonized with preparation of the protocol for real-world testing of digital cognitive assessments in WP2. Each clinical site has additionally been developing a sub-study protocol including site-specific details

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó		Security: 9/14

concerning recruitment sources and procedures, type of clinical setting (primary care and/or memory clinic), set of BBMs to be tested (based on BBMs specifications and other information provided by the relevant industry partners). Core Protocol and sub-studies are being co-designed with the relevant industry Consortium partners providing BBM assays. Common laboratory protocols (more detailed than kit inserts) have been developed for implementation across laboratories, and large volumes of internal and external quality control samples to monitor assay performances throughout the study will be collected. A core statistical analysis plan has been developed, with primary comparisons focused on the diagnostic work-up, patient flow and management at each site before and after introduction of BBMs. Appropriate ethical approvals will be obtained during 2025.

A description of key BBM-related aspects of the core protocol and sub-studies is provided below, covering four main areas: (i) blood collection, (ii) prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms, (iii) assessing the impact of BBMs on diagnostic work-up, patient flow, and management in real-world settings, and (iv) improving the use of BBMs to identify individuals with preclinical AD. As the primary focus of WP3 is on new BBMs that are currently closest to deployment in routine clinical practice, the BBMs chosen for the main analyses described below are p-tau217 related. Harmonisation with WP4 ensures sufficient blood sampling to also cover other / exploratory BBMs.

The AD-RIDDLE Core protocol and harmonisation guidelines for real-world testing of digital cognitive tools and BBMs, including an integrated framework for related objectives across WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 (i.e. *biomarker validation* and *evaluation of biomarker implementation* in real-world settings) will be made publicly available on the AD-RIDDLE website in its final form, after ethical approval is obtained at all sites. It is important to emphasize that AD-RIDDLE real-world testing is not a single study with one centralised protocol to be strictly and uniformly applied at all sites. A one-size-fits-all approach does not recognize that healthcare systems and healthcare professionals will have differing needs and preferences. AD-RIDDLE enables a more customised approach in which sites can choose from digital cognitive assessments and BBMs options to suit their needs. For example, depending on regulatory requirements or healthcare system preference, one digital cognitive assessment tool may be preferable over another; one BBM test may be incompatible with one setting yet be priority in another. As such, sites will have flexibility to assemble the set of ‘tools’ that are right for them. However, to ensure that cross site analyses can be reliably conducted, a set of common requirements will be applied.

3.1 Blood collection protocol

To ensure consistency and reliability in sample handling, the following instructions for blood collection and processing have been established:

1. **Blood Collection:** Collect blood in K2EDTA tubes.
2. **Centrifugation and Plasma Aliquoting:**
 - Centrifuge the EDTA tubes within 1 hour of collection.
 - Aliquot the plasma into LoBind tubes (e.g., Sarstedt, #72.703.600, #72.694.007).
 - Ensure the bottom part of the plasma is not extracted to avoid the buffy coat. Leave approximately 5 mm of plasma to minimize contamination.

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation	Version: v1.4 – Final	
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó	Security:	10/14

- Minimum required volume: 500 µL (for p-tau217 related BBMs selected for the main analyses)
3. **Fasting Status:** Record whether the sample was collected under fasting conditions or non-fasting conditions. If non-fasting, indicate the approximate hours since the last meal.
 4. **Temperature Control:** Keep the samples cool at 4-8 °C until shipping.
 5. **Shipping and Storage:** Ship the samples at 4-8 °C and ensure they are stored at -80 °C within 1-2 days of collection.
 6. **Analysis Timeline:** Conduct analyses of samples within 4 weeks of collection (applies to sections 3.2 and 3.3 below but is not required for 3.4). Most analyses can be performed locally, and ongoing discussions aim to finalize the comprehensive analysis plan.

These instructions have been developed collaboratively with WP4 to ensure alignment and standardization across work packages. Clinical sites participating in analyses of exploratory BBMs will collect a minimum of 10 ml blood at each study visit for local storage and further BBMs measurements (locally or as agreed with the relevant Consortium industry partners involved in exploratory BBMs analyses). Adherence to these guidelines will facilitate consistent sample quality and reliable biomarker analysis.

3.2 Prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms

A description of the key features of the observational study focusing on prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms is presented below. This protocol covers work to be conducted in WP3 Task 3.2.

AD-RIDDLE clinical sites	LU, BBRC, RS, UEF, AUMC, and IMPERIAL
BBMs selected for main analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P-tau217 • P-tau217/Aβ42 ratio • % P-tau217 • Amyloid probability score 2 (APS2, a composite score ranging from 0 to 100 which is expected to show stronger correlation with brain amyloid pathology compared with the individual biomarkers Aβ42/40 ratio or % p-tau217 considered separately). <p>All plasma samples will be analyzed within 4 weeks of blood collection.</p>
Reference standard for BBMs validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSF Aβ42/p-tau181 (Fujirebio or Roche, cutoffs as used in routine clinical practice) • Amyloid-PET (visual read as used in routine clinical practice; also 30CL in sensitivity analysis) <p>CSF and PET must be performed within maximum 6 months from plasma sampling.</p>

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó		Security: 11/14

Objective	The focus will be on conducting real-world testing of plasma p-tau217-based assays in clinical sites including memory clinics where an appropriate reference standard (i.e., CSF or PET) can be used for AD pathology confirmation.
Population	Patients with subjective cognitive decline (SCD), mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or dementia who are evaluated for the first time at a secondary or tertiary memory clinic.
Study Design	Prospective measurements of plasma samples collected up to a maximum of 4 weeks before analyses, using predefined cutoffs for determining abnormal outcomes.
Number of Participants	Estimated target n=200 patients per site (appr. for 2 years).
Main Inclusion Criteria	<p>Participants must meet ALL inclusion criteria below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with SCD, MCI or dementia who are referred to investigation for cognitive symptoms at a secondary or tertiary memory clinic. • At least 40 years of age. • After relevant clinical assessments, according to the physician, Alzheimer's disease could be a potential cause of the symptomatology. • According to the treating physician, information about potential Alzheimer's disease pathology will be relevant for patient management.
Main Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot undergo lumbar puncture or amyloid-PET imaging • Already undergone CSF or PET testing > 12 months ago
Primary Analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement (sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV) between plasma biomarker and CSF or PET biomarker outcome, when using one single predefined cutoff. • Agreement (sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV) between plasma biomarker and CSF or PET biomarker outcome, when using a two-cutoff approach (predefined). Determination of number of participants in the intermediate zone.
Secondary Analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Variation in agreement between plasma biomarker outcome and the outcome of the reference standard by cognitive status (SCD, MCI and dementia). • Variation in agreement between plasma biomarker outcome and the outcome of the reference standard by presence of relevant co-morbidities (e.g., kidney disease, diabetes, obesity etc), relevant medications, and time of day of sample collection (morning, noon, afternoon). • A sub-study will also be performed to evaluate the test-retest variability when collecting and analyzing the plasma biomarkers twice with 1-12 weeks apart in at least 50 patients per clinical site. The repeat analysis is performed on the same sample (i.e. only one blood collection).

3.3 Assessing impact of BBMs on the diagnostic work-up, patient flow and management in real-world settings

A description of the key features of the observational study assessing impact of BBMs on the diagnostic work-up, patient flow and management in real-world settings is presented below. This protocol covers work to be conducted in WP3 Task 3.3.

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó		Security: 12/14

AD-RIDDLE Clinical Sites	LU, BBRC, RS, UEF, VUmc, and IMPERIAL.
BBMs selected for main analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P-tau217 • P-tau217/Aβ42 ratio • % P-tau217 • APS2 score <p>All plasma samples will be analyzed within 4 weeks of blood collection. Based on the local clinical setup and logistics, each site will choose the BBM test which is easiest to report back to the physician. Only one BBM test will be consistently reported back to the physician at each site.</p>
Reference standard for comparison	Consensus clinical diagnosis by dementia expert(s) supported by thorough neurological, psychiatric, and cognitive assessments as well CSF AD biomarkers and/or amyloid-PET. This is established by clinicians without knowledge about the BBM test result.
Objective	We will study if diagnostic algorithms based on BBMs improve the diagnostic work-up, patient flow, and management beyond “care-as-usual” in real-world memory settings
Population	Patients with subjective cognitive decline (SCD), mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or dementia who are evaluated at a secondary or tertiary memory clinic.
Study Design	Determine whether a clinical diagnosis supported by BBM is more accurate than standard-of-care with support of any AD biomarkers. A questionnaire where the treating physician must provide information on most likely clinical diagnosis and certainty of the diagnosis is done i) before seeing the BBM results (but after clinical evaluation, cognitive testing and MRI/CT), ii) after seeing the BBM results, and iii) finally after seeing the CSF/PET results.
Number of Participants	Estimated target = 200 patients per site.
Main Inclusion Criteria	<p>Participants must meet ALL inclusion criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with SCD, MCI or dementia who undergo their first investigation for cognitive symptoms at a secondary or tertiary memory clinic. • At least 40 years of age. • After relevant clinical assessments, according to the physician Alzheimer’s disease could be a potential cause of the symptomatology. • According to the treating physician, information about potential Alzheimer’s disease pathology will be relevant for patient management.
Main Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot undergo lumbar puncture or Ab-PET imaging • Already undergone testing with BBM, CSF or PET (<12 months)
Primary Analyses	• Agreement (sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV) between i) clinical diagnosis before BBM and ii) clinical diagnosis after BBM, respectively, with the consensus clinical diagnosis supported by CSF or PET.
Secondary Analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in certainty of diagnosis after seen BBM results and then again after seeing CSF/PET results. • Question whether the physician deemed the blood test useful if not using CSF or PET (i.e. question asked after BBM results, but before CSF/PET results),

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation		Version: v1.4 – Final
	Author(s): Laia Montoliu-Gaya, Gemma Salvadó		Security: 13/14

	and whether CSF/PET was useful after BBM testing (i.e. question asked after both BBM and CSF/PET results).
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3.4 Improving the use of BBMs to identify individuals with preclinical AD

A description of the key features of the observational study for improving the use of BBMs to identify individuals with preclinical AD is presented below. This protocol covers work to be conducted in WP3 Task 3.4.

AD-RIDDLE Clinical Sites	UGOT, LU, BBRC, RS, UEF, VUmc, and IMPERIAL.
BBMs selected for main analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P-tau217 • P-tau217/Aβ42 ratio • % P-tau217 • APS2 score <p>All plasma samples to be analyzed within 4 weeks of blood collection.</p>
Reference standard for comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSF Aβ42/p-tau181 (Fujirebio or Roche, cutoffs as used in routine clinical practice) • Amyloid-PET (visual read as used in routine clinical practice; also 30CL in sensitivity analysis)
Objective	We aim to identify preclinical AD prospectively using BBMs in general populations. A secondary goal is to build a clinical trial ready cohort of people with preclinical AD.
Population	Individuals without cognitive impairment.
Study Design	To study whether plasma p-tau217-based assays can reliably detect preclinical AD when analysed prospectively. Cognitively unimpaired individuals will be screened with p-tau217-based assay tests. A subpopulation will also undergo reference standard tests (<i>enriched for those positive for BBM outcome</i>).
Number of Participants	At least 200 participants per site
Main Inclusion Criteria	Participants must meet ALL inclusion criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No cognitive impairment • At least 50 years of age.
Main Exclusion Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MCI or dementia
Primary Analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agreement (sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV) between plasma biomarker and the reference standards (CSF or PET), when using one single predefined cutoff. • Agreement (sensitivity, specificity, PPV and NPV) between plasma biomarker and the reference standards (CSF or PET), when using two different predefined cutoffs. Determination of number of participants in the intermediate zone.
Secondary Analyses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study changes in BBMs and cognitive testing in cognitively unimpaired individuals during follow-up over 2-4 years.

4. DISCUSSION

	D3.1 - Study initiation package: BBMs Core Protocol with sub-studies		
	WP3 - Real-world testing of blood-based biomarkers, including pathology confirmation	Version: v1.4 – Final	
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Across the meetings within this work package, several key decisions have been made. Deliverable 3.1 (D3.1) aims to evaluate the role of BBMs in real-world clinical settings by encompassing a diverse patient population, including individuals with potential comorbidities. This initiative represents a groundbreaking effort, as no prior study has been conducted in such a varied clinical context.

To minimize selection bias, physicians will be instructed to offer all eligible patients (based on predefined inclusion/exclusion criteria) the opportunity to participate in the study, avoiding assumptions about patient willingness beforehand. Furthermore, data will be collected on the number of patients who decline participation due to reluctance to undergo blood testing. This information will contribute to the implementation research conducted under WP5.

A dedicated meeting between WP5 and WP3 is planned to discuss strategies to ensure that WP5's evaluation extends beyond protocol adoption, addressing the broader clinical value and potential barriers to BBM implementation. Questionnaires designed to assess the impact of BBMs on clinical practice are currently in development, with efforts underway to harmonize them across participating sites, potentially with support from WP5.

The responsibility for determining assay cut-offs will lie with the laboratory teams to ensure consistency across study sites.

Logistical considerations, such as the frequency of sample shipping, remain under discussion and may vary depending on specific clinical settings. Lastly, it is emphasized that, until BBMs are formally approved for clinical use, their results will be used solely for research purposes and must not inform clinical decision-making.

In the coming months, we will proceed with tasks 3.2 (Conducting prospective validation of BBMs for the early diagnosis of AD in patients with cognitive symptoms, M12-M48) and Task 3.4 (Improving the use of BBMs to additionally identify individuals with preclinical AD, M12 – M60).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, over the past 12 months, we successfully achieved the objectives outlined in Task 3.1. We will now proceed with the next steps to accomplish the aims of Tasks 3.2 and 3.4.